

5 FOODS TO AVOID IF YOU ARE SUFFERING FROM VARICOSE VEINS

In keeping our body healthy foods always play a vital role. Many people who are suffering from venous disease start to eat unhealthy food. This will lead them to a major problem sometimes. The blood circulation in our body also depends on what we eat says the **vein specialist texas**.

If you are going through a varicose veins problem, then it is very important for you to maintain a proper healthy diet. A healthy diet gives you a strong venous system. Maintaining a proper healthy diet is not as easy as it looks. People who are unable to maintain a healthy diet went to the [vein treatment texas](#) for assistance. Read this full article to know about the foods and bad eating habits which you should avoid if you are suffering from varicose veins.

1. Refined Carbohydrates

Simple carbohydrates usually called refined carbohydrates can lead to poor vein health as well as chronic disease such as diabetes. One of the most consuming refined carbohydrates is white bread consumption on regular basis. This is a very hard habit to break. The **vein doctor near me** will suggest replacing these carbohydrates with complex ones that contain fiber. Fiber helps in reducing the pressure on the veins in your body as well as helps to reduce constipation. Whole grains, brown rice, and high fiber bread are better choices.

2. Salt and sodium

According to a **vein doctor**, sodium present in salt causes the body to retain water. Due to this, the volume of blood and blood pressure both increase. Which results in putting pressure on the venous system. In the lower extremities, the water pools retained which causes legs

and ankles to swell which contributing to varicose veins. For the venous system, a low sodium diet is best. In packaged foods, meat, pizza, olives, pickles, bacon, and soy sauce high sodium is found often.

3. Alcoholic beverages

It acts as a diuretic which results in dehydration. It affects the body. This puts extra pressure on the venous system and causes symptoms of the vasculature system. During dehydration, the body works harder to move the blood throughout these veins. So, **vein specialist** will advise you to avoid alcoholic beverages during the varicose veins

4. Added sugars

If you are going through varicose veins then you should have to choose foods that contain natural sugar. Fruits contain sugar but fresh fruits are a good choice says [vein doctor texas](#). This is because the natural sugar slowly releases into the bloodstream and fruits also contain fiber. You must avoid candies, desserts, and cookies, they contain a high amount of sugar which causes excess blood sugar and results in varicose veins problem.

5. Caffeine

The **vein treatments near me** say that blood vessels constrict due to the caffeine. But its effect is short-term and mild. Blood pressure can put a strain on your veins because varicose veins are caused by the weakening of venous walls. This elevated blood pressure can cause weakening over a period of time.